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THE ROLE OF THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN HARMONIZING LEGAL EDUCATION AND MORAL UPBRINGING IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical aspects of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan, the socio-philosophical and legal analysis of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan, the socio-educational tasks and prospects of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan are also analyzed.

Key words: education, moral education, dynamics, harmonization, social state, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis, development, legal education, social value, civil society.

Introduction

In today's context, where global moral challenges are intensifying and the need to strengthen legal mechanisms is becoming ever more urgent, the relevance of harmonizing legal education and moral upbringing is steadily increasing. This situation highlights the necessity of revisiting, reassessing, and enhancing the effectiveness of the continuous education system in integrating legal education with moral development. Unfortunately, the level of legal literacy among adolescents and young people remains very low. Quite often, the reason behind juveniles committing crimes lies in their lack of awareness regarding the legal consequences of protecting their own rights and legitimate interests. According to data from selective sociological studies, when adolescents serving sentences in correctional labor colonies were interviewed, one-third of them admitted they were unaware that their actions carried criminal liability.

In a civil society, raising the legal culture of youth is not solely a responsibility entrusted to state institutions; it also requires the active participation of public and other non-governmental organizations. Ensuring the involvement of young people in non-governmental structures and consistently improving their level of legal culture has become an urgent priority today.

Literature review and methods

The harmonization of legal education and moral upbringing, the social aspects of modernizing moral and legal education, in particular, the ways of organizing legal education in this process, the socio-legal status of moral upbringing, as well as issues of improving the quality and effectiveness of legal education and upbringing, have been studied in the works of scholars such as A. Weil, D. Easton, J. Dennis, S. Palonsky, J. Piaget, J. Kevin, J. Torney-Purta, R. Bayniyazov, N. Voplenko, O. Demko, Yu. Dmitriev, N. Keyzerov, A. Malko, N. Matuzov, V. Salnikov, L. Matveev, E. Abzalov, N. Vakhobov, D. Dehqonova, Kh. Zakirov, Z. Islomov, I. Kudryavtsev, Z. Madalieva, Kh. Mamatov, O. Nasriddinova, Kh. Odilqoriev, Y. Sadikova, A. Saidov, U. Tojikhonov, N. Saydalikhodjaeva, R. Turdiboeva, A. Khamraev, Sh. Yakubov, B. Juraev, and S. Juraev.

Results and discussion

Educational standards define the content, forms, means, and methods of education, as well as the procedures for assessing its quality. Through these standards, which constitute the core of educational content, the condition for ensuring a stable level of education across various institutions (both state and non-state) operating within the country is fulfilled. By their very nature, educational standards serve as the foundation for the development of curricula, textbooks, manuals, regulations, and other normative documents. The standard of general secondary education, in terms of its structure and content, reflects a balance between the interests and resources of the state, the region, and the school, while most importantly, it is based on the priority of the student's personality, aspirations, abilities, and interests.

In the New Uzbekistan, the harmonization of legal education and moral upbringing is carried out in law and ethics classes, which represent a consistent process aimed at achieving a specific purpose. *“The goal of harmonizing legal education and moral upbringing in the teaching of legal and moral subjects in general secondary schools is to provide students with scientific and theoretical legal knowledge, to deepen this knowledge, to identify opportunities for students to acquire legal and moral understanding, and to create pedagogical conditions necessary for developing their initial skills in organizing legal activities.”*

The objective of legal education in general secondary schools is to ensure that students understand and apply concepts related to state governance, political rights, socio-economic rights, personal rights, and duties. In particular, in grades 8–11, when teaching law subjects, it is considered appropriate to continue the educational mechanisms of the subject *“Upbringing”* taught in lower grades, which is directed toward adherence to moral norms.

To implement the tasks of the state educational standard in the field of legal education, a model of legal education has been developed. According to this model, continuous legal education is divided into separate stages, each directed toward specific goals. These stages include: legal and moral education in the family; early legal upbringing in preschool institutions; legal education in general secondary schools (primary legal education and general secondary legal education); and legal education in higher education.

Legal education must be continuous and begin at an early age. From the family and preschool institutions, children should already be acquainted with rules of behavior and receive initial understanding of moral and some legal norms. Later, this knowledge should be expanded and deepened, acquiring clearly defined legal characteristics.

Since the family is the fundamental unit of society, it plays a key role in shaping the child's personality, ensuring that they find their place in society in the future, and helping them grow into a morally mature individual. In forming legal education and upbringing, the family occupies a unique place, guided by the goals and tasks of each stage of the child's development.

In grades 1–4 of general secondary schools, within the subject *“Upbringing”*, simple concepts such as rule, law, duty, and responsibility are introduced to students in accordance with their age-specific characteristics, and these are integrated into the content of the topics. At this stage, students begin to develop legal literacy. First and foremost, they learn the meaning of the word *“law”*, the essence of human rights, the rights of the child, and how to interact with others in accordance with the norms of legal culture. They also acquire an understanding of such concepts as *“this is mine, this is ours, this belongs to someone else, this belongs to the majority.”*

From the perspective of applying their legal knowledge in practice, students are required to master the following skills and competencies: analyzing the possible consequences of violating rules, such as disregarding traffic light signals; collaborating effectively with peers; adhering to rules of etiquette when expressing their opinions; developing habits of rational interaction with the environment; making efforts to maintain their health; observing moral and behavioral norms; managing their time effectively and following a daily routine.

Taking into account students' acquisition of these skills and in accordance with the standards set for legal upbringing at this level, lessons are organized and educational materials are developed. Moreover, from the standpoint of legal knowledge, students are expected to master a number of important concepts,

such as: complying with the rules established in the classroom, school, and public spaces; recognizing and fulfilling the duty to protect nature; respecting the opinions of peers; obeying road signs, warning and directive signs, and traffic light signals; and adhering to norms of behavior and standards of polite communication. These skills and competencies are those which children at this age must acquire, and teachers instill them in students by taking their developmental level into account.

Overall, legal education and moral upbringing are organized according to the principle of progression from the simple to the complex. Specifically, in the lower grades, legal knowledge is integrated with moral norms, while in the upper grades students are gradually introduced to more complex legal relationships.

In grades 8–11, within the subject *“Fundamentals of State and Law”*, the initial concepts are expanded and complicated through real-life examples, covering such topics as the relationship between the state and the individual, personal independence, equality before the law, freedom of speech, guarantees of access to information, and knowledge related to the criminal liability of minors. Their knowledge of the Constitution, the state, and the law is reinforced, and they develop an understanding of the essence of the Constitution. Students come to realize that education is guaranteed by the state, that laws must be observed unconditionally, and that violating the rights of others is contrary to the Constitution.

At this stage, from the standpoint of acquiring legal knowledge and moral upbringing, students are expected to master the following: understanding their rights, duties, and responsibilities and adhering to them; respecting the opinions of classmates and peers; protecting school property; keeping their clothes and learning materials neat; following etiquette and joining in when the national anthem is performed; refraining from fighting with peers and respecting the inviolability of others; complying with established rules and codes of conduct at school and in the community; and adhering to the student code of conduct.

Furthermore, from the perspective of developing an active civic position, students are expected to acquire a range of additional competencies, such as: analyzing which behaviors may lead to legal violations; realizing that education is a compulsory duty for all; recognizing that everyone is equal before the law; evaluating the legality of their own actions; actively participating in community affairs; and drawing conclusions about the importance of peace, national welfare, secure borders, and the rule of law.

In the subject “*Fundamentals of State and Law*”, the main task of legal education and upbringing is to form in students a system of knowledge that corresponds to the socio-economic, political-legal, scientific, and cultural development directions of our country, as well as to shape citizens who can think creatively and express independent opinions regarding real-life problems.

Conclusion.

The development of society and the progress of production, to a certain extent, depend on the content and level of education provided to the younger generation, as well as on the orientation, essence, and results of the teaching carried out in educational institutions functioning in this sphere. Indeed, the qualitative and substantive advancement of the educational system makes it possible to provide students with legal knowledge, introduce the latest achievements of science, technology, and innovation into the educational process, achieve high results with less physical effort and time, and cultivate and enrich moral and ethical qualities in individuals. On this basis, a spiritually, morally, and legally sound lifestyle can be established in society. Wherever such a moral-legal environment and healthy way of life are achieved, overall development in all spheres of society becomes possible.

The significance of legal sciences in the system of continuous education, in developing the legal and moral upbringing of students and youth, lies in the fact that through these subjects students not only acquire legal knowledge but also develop respect for the law and a commitment to abide by it. For this purpose, legal educators must possess not only strong knowledge but also moral maturity and professional skills.

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